

Climateurope2

Deliverable 4.8 Consolidated set of training modules available online

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Climateurope2

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Term
CS	Climate Service(s)
WP	Work Package

About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate Services (CS) address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and needs for climate information have seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of CS are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines and good practices) for CS are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of CS, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured CS to all sectors of society by:

1. Developing standardisation procedures for CS
2. Supporting an equitable European CS community
3. Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured CS to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of CS, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of CS, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European CS will also be organised.

Executive Summary

The Climateurope2 project aims to strengthen the European Climate Services (CS) landscape by advancing equitable, high-quality services that support informed decision-making for climate adaptation and mitigation across society. A core ambition of the project is to improve the credibility and uptake of Climate Services by fostering standardisation, strengthening the CS community, and stimulating market development. Within this context, Work Package 4 (WP4) focuses on market development, with the co-design of training modules serving as a key instrument to support both knowledge brokerage and market stimulation.

Training modules were developed to address persistent challenges in the CS domain, including uneven understanding of Climate Services concepts, limited awareness of their practical application, and gaps in technical and professional capacity across the wider Climate Services ecosystem. Although Climate Services are increasingly recognised as essential, many actors - including policymakers, private sector organisations, researchers, journalists, educators, service providers, early-career professionals, and civil society organisations - require additional support to effectively understand, communicate, develop, apply, and use Climate Services. The modules therefore serve as accessible, structured educational resources that translate complex CS knowledge into practical, usable formats. Training module topics include standardisation, innovation in CS, best- and malpractices, data principles, co-production, business models, and science communication - equipping learners to recognise, request, develop, and apply Climate Services effectively.

To ensure relevance, quality, and legitimacy, the development of the training modules followed a co-creation approach involving all relevant Climateurope2 work packages. This approach reflected the interdisciplinary nature of Climate Services and ensured that scientific, technical, market, and societal perspectives were fully integrated. The process began with internal scoping within WP4, followed by consortium-wide engagement through the 2023 General Assembly, an exploitation workshop, bilateral exchanges with WP leads, and ongoing coordination until module submission. A key guiding principle was efficiency: partners were encouraged to transform existing project outputs - such as workshops, webinars, and methodological deliverables - into training modules, reducing duplication while maximising impact.

Three main training module formats were adopted: short-form videos, guidance documents, and recordings or reports of training sessions from project events. These formats were selected to balance quality, accessibility, and resource awareness, and were supported by common guidance and a shared visual identity. The resulting modules are organised into three categories on the Climateurope2 platform: (1) Educational/Informative modules, (2) Instructional modules and Guidance, and (3) Reports from training sessions held during events.

The co-creation process culminated in a consolidated set of training modules, jointly produced by multiple work packages and tailored to diverse target audiences, including CS providers and users, researchers, policymakers, journalists, educators, and platform users. These modules were tested with stakeholders and informed by feedback from the CS community, notably during the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade (2025) and the 5th Climateurope2 Webstival (April 2026). Hands-on testing, feedback exercises, and wider dissemination ensured that the modules are both practically usable and aligned with stakeholder needs.

All training modules are disseminated via the [Climateurope2 platform](#), a publicly accessible, interactive repository that connects training content with related project outputs such as technical deliverables, recommendations for standardisation and CS best practices. This integration enhances visibility, usability, and long-term value, positioning the platform as a central hub for Climate Services knowledge.

Keywords

Market Stimulation, Knowledge Brokerage, Capacity Building, Training Modules, Climate Services Market

1. Introduction

Climateurope2 is committed to advancing the next generation of equitable, high-quality Climate Services (CS) that can be applied across all sectors of society. The project seeks to strengthen the CS market and landscape in Europe by supporting the development of standardisation procedures, strengthening an inclusive CS community, and promoting the wider uptake of reliable and fit-for-purpose CS. These efforts aim to enhance both climate adaptation and mitigation capacities in response to ongoing climate change and variability.

Within this broader mission, Work Package (WP) 4 focuses specifically on market development. A key element of this work is the co-design of training modules that have the stated goals of market stimulation and knowledge brokerage. The co-design process, which is introduced and explained in this document, lays the foundation for the creation of high-quality training content that reflects the breadth of knowledge created in the Climateurope2 project. This report outlines the themes and scope of the training modules, the co-creation process, and the dissemination of the modules through the Climateurope2 platform and their further dissemination within the broader Climateurope2 community.

1.1. Objectives and Scope

The central objective of the development of training content within Climateurope2 was to create training modules tailored to the specific needs related to knowledge brokerage and market stimulation in the CS domain. These terms are further defined in [Chapter 2](#).

While many definitions of CS exist, the Climateurope2 project uses the following definition. Climate Services involve the provision of climate information in such a way as to assist decision-making. The service includes appropriate engagement from users and providers, is based on scientifically credible information and expertise, has an effective access mechanism and responds to user needs.

These can include climate projections, forecasts, impact assessments, economic analyses, best-practice guidance, the development and evaluation of climate solutions, and other services that help society understand and respond to climate-related risks and opportunities.

Despite the growing importance of CS, their understanding and use across society remain limited. Many potential users—including public institutions, private companies, and civil society—are still unfamiliar with how CS can support decision-making, and there are persistent knowledge gaps in the broader CS ecosystem on topics such as standardisation, co-creation, and communication of data.

Climateurope2 aims to bridge this knowledge gap through targeted activities, and the development of comprehensive training modules supports this effort.

The training modules serve as educational tools or guidance that introduce learners to essential concepts and practices within the CS field. Topics range from CS standardisation to business models and best practices to design and deliver effective CS. By offering structured, accessible content, the modules provide users with the knowledge needed to recognise, request, develop, and implement CS that meet their needs.

2. The aim of the Training Modules

The aim of creating training modules within the Climateurope2 project, as outlined in the project objectives, is to support **knowledge brokerage** and **market stimulation** in the context of CS. Below, these terms as they relate to the CS market are explained in detail.

2.1. Knowledge Brokerage

Knowledge brokerage on Climate Services refers to the process of connecting people who produce climate information (e.g., scientists) with those who use it (e.g., policymakers, businesses, or communities). It involves translating complex data into clear, useful, and relevant knowledge that supports better decisions for adapting to climate change. Knowledge brokers, i.e. actors who are translating the data, can be individuals or organisations, and they work across public, private, and non-profit sectors. Their role is to bridge gaps, build trust, and make Climate Services easier to understand and use.

The training modules can be understood as supporting knowledge brokerage, as they clearly communicate complex topics (such as standardisation, FAIR data principles, or the co-creation of CS) in short-form content like videos or guidance documents that will make CS easier to understand for their audience.

2.2. Market Stimulation

Market stimulation for Climate Services refers to strategies or actions taken by a company, government, or organisation to encourage demand for a product or service in a market ecosystem centred around Climate Services. Market stimulation efforts in the context of Climate Services

typically involve creating a demand for Climate Services, capacity building, Climate Service market research and assessment, funding and investment in Climate Services, and information sharing and collaboration.

The training modules aim to stimulate the CS market through capacity building and the sharing of knowledge created in the Climateurope2 project with the audience of CS market actors (end users, journalists, scientists, CS providers, researchers, early-career professionals, etc.).

3. The Co-Creation Process

Developing effective training modules within Climateurope2 required a collaborative approach from the start. Because the work conducted in the Climateurope2 project spans a wide range of scientific, technical, and societal dimensions, no single WP could provide all the insights needed to design high-quality and relevant training content. For this reason, co-creation was chosen as the guiding methodology. By involving all relevant WPs, the project aimed to integrate expertise from climate science, user engagement, data infrastructures, market analysis, and business development. This interdisciplinary input ensures that the training modules are both scientifically robust and practically useful for diverse audiences.

Co-creation also strengthens the credibility and legitimacy of the modules. When content reflects the collective knowledge of the consortium, it becomes more representative of the project's work and more aligned with stakeholder needs. In this way, co-creation helps guarantee that the resulting modules meet high internal standards while remaining accessible and impactful for learners inside and outside the Climateurope2 community.

3.1 Timeline of the Co-Creation Process

The co-creation process began with internal discussions within WP4, where the objectives, scope, and intended users of the training modules were defined. Early on, it became clear that the modules should draw on knowledge already being produced across the project. This decision formed the basis for a broader consortium-wide collaboration.

The first public introduction of the task took place during the Climateurope2 General Assembly on 14–15 September 2023, where the consortium received a brief overview of the planned co-creation

approach. This initial presentation served to signal that contributions from multiple WPs would be essential.

An important next step was the Exploitation workshop held on 18 September 2023, where a dedicated brainstorming session brought together members from several WPs to jointly reflect on potential training module topics. This was the first structured opportunity for cross-consortium input and generated a wide range of ideas that informed the next stages of the process.

Following the workshop, WP4 initiated a series of bilateral and multilateral exchanges with other WPs. These interactions included bilateral email consultations with WP leaders, participation in weekly WP meetings, and a presentation during a joint meeting of WP1–6. The purpose of this outreach was to raise awareness of the task, explore possible contributions, and identify existing materials or activities that could be transformed into training modules.

Bilateral communication with WP leads, as well as communication to the whole consortium on key deadlines, continued until the end of March 2026, by which time all modules were submitted to WP4.

A central principle throughout has been efficiency and resource awareness. WPs were encouraged to build on material already being developed as part of their scheduled project activities—such as workshops, stakeholder engagement tasks, webinars, or methodological outputs. Translating these into training modules reduces duplication of effort while ensuring that the modules reflect concrete CS work being conducted within the project. This approach allows the consortium to produce high-quality content without placing unnecessary additional demands on WPs.

Overall, the co-creation process has progressed through internal planning, consortium briefings, collaborative brainstorming, and targeted bilateral engagement with individual WPs. This structured approach has ensured that the development of CS training modules is both inclusive and grounded in the diverse expertise distributed across Climateurope2.

This collaborative approach helped ensure the modules were scientifically robust, practically relevant, and aligned with the target audience's needs. Ultimately, the goal was to develop materials that meet the high standards established across the project while also being accessible and impactful for learners inside the wider Climateurope2 community.

3.2 Training Module Formats

To ease the workload of WPs, WP4 provided guidance on the format, style, and - where necessary - content of the training modules. This guidance was sent out to WPs in emails, and it was accessible to them on a designated page in the internal project wiki.

The formats that were considered included:

3.2.1 Shortform Videos

These videos delivered concise explanations or insights that enhance understanding and provide new knowledge related to market stimulation and knowledge brokerage in the field of climate services. They are submitted in video file format, which can be hosted on the Climateurope2 platform, and would be between 5 and 15 minutes long. They would include the template training module title page developed by Climate KIC for a coherent visual identity across all training modules.

3.2.2 Guidance Documents

These documents summarise essential concepts and guide the audience through a clear, step-by-step process, presented in an engaging visual format. They are submitted in PDF format, including, where possible, visuals, graphics, or images. They would include the template training module title page developed by Climate KIC for a coherent visual identity across all training modules.

3.2.3 Records of training sessions

These could be video recordings of sessions conducted during, e.g. Climateurope2 Webstivals or online stakeholder webinars/workshops or minutes collected during an in-person training. They were included on the platform - with permission of the speakers - due to their valuable content and insights presented. This format corresponds to the training module category “*Reports of Training Sessions from Events*” explained in [Section 4.3](#) below.

4. Training Module Categories

The training modules available through the Climateurope2 platform support capacity development, market stimulation, and the uptake of CS across Europe. They are co-created by project partners and integrated into an interactive platform environment. Together, they contribute to building a more

coherent and equitable CS ecosystem by increasing climate literacy, supporting standardisation, and encouraging the demand and use of CS.

The modules fall into three main categories, which are reflected on the platform (see Fig. 1) and explained in more detail below. A fourth category (All Training Modules) allows the user to access all the modules together.

Training Modules

The Climateurope2 project provides a set of Training Modules designed to enhance the understanding and uptake of Climate Services across Europe. These modules support knowledge brokerage and market stimulation, two strategic goals that help build a robust and equitable Climate Services ecosystem. The modules bridge knowledge gaps and empower stakeholders to make informed decisions in response to climate variability and change. Integrated into this Climateurope2 platform, the Training Modules are co-created by various project partners, ensuring they reflect diverse expertise and reflect the breadth of work that is being conducted across the project.

The Climateurope2 Training Modules build capacity, support standardisation efforts, and stimulate demand for Climate Services, contributing to Climateurope2's mission of advancing climate adaptation and mitigation across sectors.

The available modules are distinguished into 3 categories, based on their type of content:

1. Educational / Informative Training Modules
2. Instructional Training Module / Guidance
3. Reporting of Training Module sessions held during events

Fig 1. Categories of training modules on the Climateurope2 platform.

4.1. Educational / Informative Training Modules

These modules are structured, self-contained learning units that introduce specific knowledge, concepts, or skills. They break down complex topics into manageable components to make learning more engaging and accessible. These modules have a more education-focused approach, suggesting further study or exercises to the audience, e.g. through provided research questions or reading lists. Such modules may be used as part of courses, training programmes, or independent study.

Example: *Best Practices and Malpractices for Stimulation of the Climate Service Market*

<https://platform.climateurope2.eu/documents/training/3>

4.2. Instructional Training Modules / Guidance

An instructional training module or guidance is a focused unit of instruction designed to guide the audience through or teach a specific competency, skill, or topic, to directly make informed decisions in trainees' management, maintenance, personal, social or educational steps. The content has a particular focus on the use of climate services and is self-contained.

Example: *Introduction to the Climateurope2 Platform*

<https://platform.climateurope2.eu/documents/training/5>

4.3. Reports of Training Sessions from Events

This category includes documentation, in the form of recordings or minutes, from training sessions delivered during Climateurope2 events, whether online or in person. These reports offer insights into the structure, content, and delivery of past sessions, including the types of interactions used and the topics addressed. They are particularly valuable for understanding how climate-related training is applied in real settings, such as at the annual Climateurope2 Festival or other Climateurope2 events like Webstivals or stakeholder webinars.

Example: *Numbers are not Enough?! - Science Communication & Journalism*

<https://platform.climateurope2.eu/documents/training/4>

5. *Publishing the Training Modules - The Climateurope2 Platform*

The publication strategy for the training modules involves their integration into the Climateurope2 platform, where the consolidated set of training modules is publicly available as of May 2026. The [Climateurope2 platform](#), developed by WP7, is a dynamic web application, strategically designed to serve as an interactive and user-friendly repository for key project results that will remain as project legacy. It encompasses materials and publications on good practices, recommendations, vocabularies, a community engagement component, and more.

This platform, essentially functioning as a library for CS-related materials, allows users not only to view but also to interact with and comment on various project outcomes. The interactive features contribute to a richer user experience, fostering engagement and collaboration within the Climateurope2 community.

A distinctive feature of the platform is its ability to **present the training modules alongside relevant project outcomes** such as documents and case studies (see Fig. 2 below). This strategic alignment enhances the visibility of both the training modules and other project outcomes and creates a cohesive and comprehensive resource for users.

In summary, the integration of training modules into the Climateurope2 platform signifies a commitment to accessibility, interactivity, and community engagement. This platform acts as a central hub for Climateurope2 outputs, supporting visibility, accessibility, and knowledge sharing across the climate services community.

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Training Module
[Best Practices and Malpractices for Stimulation of the Climate Service Market](#)

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Recommendations for Assessing and Increasing the Impact of Climate Services

Abstract

D4.6 provides a cohesive assessment of the current state of the Climate Services (CS) market, consisting of insights gained from an eDelphi study with key CS market actors as well as an in-depth analysis of the relevant scientific publications on the topic of CS impact assessment and increase. An updated, ranked, catalogue of best practices and malpractices was provided and summarised, along with recommendations for increasing and assessing the impact of CS. A step-by-step process for assessing the impact of CS was introduced:

1. Define the evaluation purpose and scope
2. Develop an impact pathway as part of project design
3. Define a baseline
4. Select the appropriate evaluation methodology (qualitative or quantitative)
5. Account for attribution and confounding factors
6. Reflect on external validity and scalability

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Climateurope2

Recommendations for Assessing and Increasing the Impact of Climate Services

D4.6 provides a cohesive assessment of the current state of the Climate Services (CS) market, consisting of insights gained from an eDelphi study with key CS market actors as well as an in-depth analysis of the relevant scientific publications on the topic of CS impact assessment and increase. An updated, ranked, catalogue of best practices and malpractices was provided and summarised, along with recommendations for increasing and assessing the impact of CS. A step-by-step process for assessing the impact of CS was introduced:

1. Define the evaluation purpose and scope
2. Develop an impact pathway as part of project design
3. Define a baseline
4. Select the appropriate evaluation methodology (qualitative or quantitative)
5. Account for attribution and confounding factors
6. Reflect on external validity and scalability

The full set of recommendations issued in this report is summarised below:

Fig 2. Example page from the Climateurope2 platform showing how a training module can be displayed next to a thematically relevant publication.

6. The consolidated set of Training Modules

The process of co-creation described in detail in the previous section culminated in a consolidated set of submitted training modules available online on the Climateurope2 platform.

These modules were developed together with other WPs over the duration of the project. The following Table 1 provides an overview of the full set of 10 submitted modules, including a short description of the module's content and which of the aforementioned three categories it falls under. Where relevant, the target audience for the module is also indicated.

Table 1: Overview of the consolidated set of training modules available on the Climateurope2 platform as of May 2026.

Module Title	Module Description	Lead WP	Target Audience	Category and Format
Standardisation	<i>This module covers the fundamentals of standardisation, including what it is, various types of standards, the process of developing standards, their applications in industry, as well as the benefits they offer.</i>	WP1	Providers and users of CS and other participants in the market	Cat: Educational / Informative Training Modules Form: Video
Implementing Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): A Practical Guide to Building Robust, Referenceable Data Repositories	<p><i>In the era of Open Science, a "broken link" is more than just a nuisance—it's a barrier to reproducibility. A Persistent Identifier (PID) provides a permanent, immutable path to a resource, ensuring that data remains discoverable and correctly cited throughout its lifecycle.</i></p> <p><i>While the use of PIDs is a cornerstone of the FAIR principles and a core recommendation for Climateurope2 (Work Package 2), a practical knowledge gap remains. Many developers understand the theory but lack the technical roadmap to implement PIDs within their own repository architectures.</i></p> <p><i>This training module bridges that gap. Readers will move beyond the "why" and dive into the "how" of building repositories that support PIDs. This material will provide data managers with the tools to comply with current best practices and stay ahead of emerging data regulations, ensuring their climate services remain authoritative and referenceable.</i></p>	WP2	<p>Primary: Data managers, software developers, and technical leads within climate service providers.</p> <p>Secondary: Researchers and project coordinators interested in the technical implementation of FAIR data principles.</p>	Cat: Instructional Training Module / Guidance Form: Guidance document
Crafting Business Innovation in Climate Services	<i>This module explores how business models and innovation strategies can enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of climate services, with a focus on supporting transformational climate adaptation. Using the Business Model Canvas and empirical interviews with providers, it identifies key</i>	WP3	Practitioners, researchers, and service developers	Cat: Educational / Informative Training Modules Form: Video

	<i>practices, challenges, and opportunities across public and private sectors. The module provides recommendations to improve climate service design, delivery, and impact for building climate-resilient societies.</i>			
Best Practices and Malpractices for Stimulation of the Climate Service Market	<i>Based on the research conducted for the Climateurope2 deliverable D4.3, this training module introduces key best practices and malpractices that are influencing the climate service market. It further describes methods for assessing climate service impact and describes key developments and trends that will impact the CS market in the future. For further information, please consult D4.3.</i>	WP4	Providers and users of CS and other participants in the market	Cat: Educational / Informative training modules Form: Video
Co-production of climate services for policy support	<i>This teaching module introduces climate services as socially embedded practices shaped by decision contexts, institutions, and interactions between scientists, policymakers, and users. It explores key concepts such as co-production, knowledge systems, trust, quality, and standardisation to explain how climate services function and are used in practice.</i>	WP5	CS providers, policy makers, citizen initiatives, academics	Cat: Educational / Informative Training Modules Form: Guidance document
How to use the Climateurope2 platform	<i>This tutorial video introduces the four main sections of the Climateurope2 platform, Explore, Connect, Analytics, and Co-create. Each section is demonstrated in this order, highlighting its key features and functionalities.</i>	WP7	Users of the CE2 platform	Cat: Instructional Training Module / Guidance Form: Video
Guidance on how to set up a 'train the trainers' module	<i>The "Train the Trainer" Module is a guidance on how to set up a Module to train on skills, techniques, and knowledge needed to deliver effective and engaging training sessions to learners in the field of climate services in various professional settings.</i>	WP7	CS Educators	Cat: Instructional Training Module / Guidance Form: Guidance document
Climate Change Communication for Journalists	<i>This module is designed for journalists and provides a clear overview of how climate data are produced, sourced, and integrated, including the role of climate models in generating projections and scenarios. It introduces the IPCC risk framework, explaining how climate data are used to identify hazards and assess risks in relation to exposure, vulnerability and response. The module also addresses key concepts such as uncertainty and event</i>	WP7	Journalists	Cat: Educational / Informative Training Modules Form: Video and accompanying PDF

	<i>attribution, helping participants understand how scientific evidence is interpreted and communicated by authoritative sources. Overall, it offers essential foundations in climate science, equipping participants with the knowledge and analytical tools needed for accurate, data-driven reporting and for addressing climate-related misinformation.</i>			
Numbers are not Enough?! - Science Communication & Journalism	<i>This module is based on a recording from one of Climateurope2's stakeholders' perspectives webinars. The webinar had the focus of communication and journalism, and the module includes the presentation of Vladimir Djurdjevic from the University of Belgrade on effective science communication.</i>	N/A	Journalists and science communicators	Cat: Reporting of Training Module sessions held during events Form: Video
FAIR data principles in the co-creation of climate services	<i>Fair data principles in the co-creation of climate services' was organized. All the presentations given during this training have been compiled into a single PowerPoint document. The accompanying reflection document contributes to project's capacity building task by making explicit the trainers' choices made in the design, implementation and evaluation of the training, the results of these choices and some lessons learnt by the trainers.</i>	WP7	Early-career professionals, master and PhD students involved in climate studies, water management, urban planning or related fields who are interested in the development of climate information	Cat: Reporting of training module sessions held during events Form: Guidance document

7. Training Module Audience Engagement

Both the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade in September 2025 and the 5th Climateurope2 Webstival in April 2026 provided important opportunities to test the modules with their intended audience and collect feedback on the training modules from the wider CS community. At the Belgrade Festival, participants engaged directly with a draft module in a hands-on setting, allowing the project team to observe how its content functioned in practice and gather structured user feedback.

The Webstival, held in April 2026, then expanded this process by presenting the consolidated set of training modules to the broader Climateurope2 network, enabling wider visibility, discussion, and continued refinement. Together, these events ensured that the modules were evaluated through both in-depth practical application and broader community dissemination.

Further information on the events is given below.

7.1 The 2025 Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade

The training session held during the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade provided a valuable real-world opportunity to test and validate a CS training module directly with the CS community. Over the course of three structured sessions, participants engaged with the module content on FAIR data principles and the co-creation of CS, applying it in practice by developing a CS plan for a real end user from the BioSense Institute. The interactive format—combining presentations, hands-on group work, and direct engagement with the end user—allowed participants to trial the module’s concepts and tools in a realistic decision-support setting.

Importantly, the session concluded with a Mentimeter-based feedback exercise, through which participants provided insights into what worked well, what remained challenging, and what additional training topics they perceived as necessary. This feedback, captured in the [session minutes](#), highlights difficulties such as understanding stakeholder needs and navigating data sources, as well as interest in further skill-building areas such as software tools and data availability. Because participants represented early-career researchers from diverse disciplinary backgrounds and engaged in an authentic co-creation process, their input constitutes meaningful testing and validation of the module’s relevance, clarity, and usability within the broader CS community.

7.2 The 5th Climateurope2 Webstival - April 2026

During the 5th Climateurope2 Webstival, held online April 15th to 17th 2026, the training modules were presented to the Climateurope2 community (see Fig. 3 below). Attendees were encouraged to engage with the set of modules that were available at the time of the Webstival, while also mentioning that the completed set would be uploaded by the end of May 2026.

The continued dissemination of the training modules through the platform, as well as Climateurope2's social channels (e.g. LinkedIn), ensures that the target audience of the modules is maximised.

Explore our training modules

Educational / Informative Training Modules

These modules are designed to build capacity, support standardisation, and stimulate the demand and uptake of Climate Services across Europe.

Find them in the “Explore” section of the Climateurope2 Platform.

Instructional Training Module / Tutorial

Topics include:

- Crafting Business Innovation in Climate Services
- Best Practices & Malpractices for the Stimulation of the Climate Service Market
- Co-Production of Climate Services for Policy Support

And more!

Report of Training Module sessions held during events

Coordinated by **Barcelona Supercomputing Center**
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Fig. 3 Slide shown during the 5th Webstival, alerting the audience that the modules are now available online

7.3 Additional Outreach & Dissemination

To further maximise the awareness and dissemination of the Climateurope2 training modules, the plan is to promote them through upcoming stakeholder engagement activities, such as stakeholders' perspectives webinars and via the Climateurope2 social media channels (e.g. LinkedIn, Bluesky). A social media campaign is planned for the dissemination of training modules, with a first post that announces the full series and follow-up posts focusing on individual modules and their particularities. The campaign will be run by WP7 during Summer 2026, a period in which project activities tend to slow down, and this type of communication content is particularly useful to keep engagement.

8. *Conclusion and Summary*

Over the duration of the Climateurope2 project, the development of training modules has taken place through an iterative and collaborative process, as outlined in [Chapter 3](#). This co-creation approach emphasised the goal of achieving a dynamic and interactive training module creation that was both resource-efficient and a way for WPs to disseminate their findings and results in a stakeholder-facing manner.

The expertise of the WPs played a crucial role in ensuring high-quality module content, as well as an effective transfer of knowledge. The WP's specialised knowledge was harnessed to contribute valuable insights and domain-specific information, enriching the substance of the training modules.

Throughout the co-creation process, active support was provided by WP4 and by the task leaders Climate KIC. This assistance extended beyond mere content creation and included guidance in the selection of module formats. Tailoring the modules to cater to their intended audience is a key focus, ensuring that the training materials are not only informative but also effectively resonate with the specific needs and characteristics of their target audience.

To conclude, the development of training modules was a joint cross-project venture, where the unique expertise of the WPs was complemented by support from WP4. The collaborative and iterative approach, coupled with tailored support, yielded training modules that stand out in quality, relevance, and effectiveness. The training modules contribute to their stated goal of knowledge brokerage and market stimulation, raising awareness for CS, and building capacity in the field of CS for relevant stakeholders.